

A multi-faceted evaluation framework to evaluate service providers' and travellers' experience with MaaS enabling technologies

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Abstract

The concept of Mobility as a Service (MaaS) has been recently introduced to transportation and has the potential to really affect and change the transportation market as well as the interactions between users, service providers and suppliers across many countries. The aim was to firstly evaluate the usefulness, ease of use, usability and user experience of travellers and service providers in using the MaaS enabling mobile application and Service Registration Tool, respectively and secondly to evaluate the user experience and adoption of both solutions in in real-life continuous use for 6 months in 5 European cities (Amsterdam, Athens, Prague, Rome, Salzburg) for national and cross-border journeys. This paper presents a multifaceted evaluation framework for the evaluation of a MaaS mobile application by travellers and preliminary findings from the user experience tests.

Keywords: MaaS; mobile application; usability; user experience; service providers; aggregators; evaluation framework.

1. Introduction

The concept of Mobility as a Service (MaaS) has been recently introduced to transportation and has the potential to really affect and change the transportation market as well as the interactions between users, service providers and suppliers across many countries. The MaaS concept is a ‘*mobility distribution model in which a customer’s major transportation needs are met over one interface and are offered by a service provider*’ (Hietanen, 2014).

Growing transportation needs, the increasing population and the growing demand of citizens for integrated services in combination with the rise of disruptive technologies, Internet of Things and the habits of new generations have led to the concept of Mobility as a Service (MaaS) as the solution to personalised, flexible and on-demand mobility needs. MaaS aims to bring private and public transport operators together and integrate the different forms of transport into one single, on-demand mobility service while placing end users at the centre of transport services and workings towards providing them with customized mobility solutions based on their needs.

MyCorridor is a Horizon2020 EU project (www.mycorridor.eu/) that aims to deliver a ‘MaaS ecosystem-to-be’ prototype. The MyCorridor project explores the design, development and use of an all-inclusive one stop shop for Mobility as a Service (MaaS) packages as an enabler for seamless and sustainable mobility. This is accommodated by bringing together the MaaS ecosystem (data, service and technology providers, TMC and infrastructure operators, C-ITS and ICT third party providers, authorities and other decision makers and finally, all types of travellers) throughout novel business models, in the context of which the focal role is played by the so-called MaaS aggregator(s)/issuer(s). The Mycorridor one-stop-shop aims at providing multimodal and cross-border mobility, infomobility (supporting mobility), added value (enhancing mobility) and traffic management services; all in a personalised manner. Travellers interaction with the one-stop-shop were made through mobile apps in Android and iOS and for service providers, through a semantics-based service registration tool.

At the end of the project, the MyCorridor mobile application will be ready to be deployed in the transportation market– standalone or in integration with other MaaS one-stop-shops - and used by real travellers to accommodate for the existing and new services. Hence, the operation of this mobile app will entail multi-faceted and complex interactions that have not been evaluated in-depth in the past and, as such, there are no standard or typical methods to evaluate their use and value.

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The evaluation activities of this project entail the participation of service and transportation providers, developers, research institutes, transportation companies, and various SMEs in 5 pilot sites across Europe (Austria, Czech Republic, Greece, Italy, and The Netherlands) as well as additional cross-border corridors that pass from several countries, connecting different pilot sites with the participation of over 400 travellers and 30 service providers in two separate phases. At the end of evaluation activities, stakeholder focus groups - with representatives from government/authorities, cities/regions, mobility and MaaS operators and aggregators, transportation providers/operators, infomobility, added value and mobile service/ technology providers and travellers - will be held to support the supplementary impact assessment (MAMCA), as well as to collect feedback about the added value of the developed MaaS technologies to the MaaS and, generally, the transportation market and facilitate in identifying the necessary steps to be taken to create the conditions for a sustainable and growing MaaS one-stop-shop.

The overarching aim is to evaluate the use and user experience of travellers and service providers in using the MaaS mobile application with different mobility products (services, or combination of services), available in different pilot sites through pre-determined and/ or customised MaaS packages. This paper presents the methodological design and framework created and adopted across Europe in step-wise fashion.

1.1. Objectives

The aim was to create a multi-faceted evaluation framework for the evaluation of this MaaS mobile application as well as of an online service registration solution for service providers to be able to integrate their services to this mobile application:

- Evaluating the usefulness, ease of use, usability and user experience of travellers and service providers in using the MyCorridor mobile ap (1st iteration) and Service Registration Tool, respectively – *mostly formative/ partially summative*.
- Evaluating the user experience of the MyCorridor mobile app in a semi-real-life (i.e. travellers use the mobile application in real conditions but only for pre-defined journeys where the integrated services are available) use in a longitudinal condition with both main clusters of users for a longer period – *summative evaluation, collection of analytics and online feedback forms (incl. benchmarking evaluation)*.

2. The methodology of a multi-faceted and iterative evaluation framework

Evaluation activities are iterative for both major user clusters- that interact directly with the MaaS one-stop-shop- with an additional participatory focus groups' round. An iterative approach within and across user groups is adopted to allow for two dimensions:

- Fragmented evaluations that focus on certain parts of the platform and the potential interactions users can have with the MaaS/mobile application;
- An optimisation process to take in place with focus on delivering a usable and useful MaaS platform, accessible to all traveller types.

The user's role is central in the evaluation from the beginning of the development process; as such, a one-stop-shop experience in transportation is innovative but rather complex and complicated. Hence, the primary focus is delivering MaaS enabling solutions that will evoke positive experience to users, but the validation of the selected pre-defined MaaS packages is also important, as are the chosen incentives per interaction type, e.g. differentiation of incentives between un-registered and registered users. A feedback loop mechanism was set between the evaluation teams and the development teams as soon each evaluation phase will be completed.

2.1. Evaluation dimensions, indicators and success criteria

This evaluation framework is user-centred and multi-faceted, i.e. it addresses 2 major clusters of users (service providers and travellers), in 4 types of evaluation activities (co-participatory, formative and usability testing, real-life and benchmarking experience, impact assessment). Apart from the co-design phase, the remaining three evaluation activities are closely connected and follow an iterative approach.

Apart from a multi-faceted evaluation, the approach adopted is mixed, as it includes interviews, questionnaires (some of them standardised), travel diaries (for the second phase) as well as co-participatory design focus groups that will be conducted before the beginning of the first iteration to resolve any design problems, issues and indecisions.

Evaluation for service providers, as well for the first iteration phase with travellers, is ex-ante and ex-post; however, evaluation for travellers in the second phase will be ex-ante, in-itinere and ex-post. The addition of in-itinere condition in the second evaluation phase is possible because travellers will make real journeys and not only user testing sessions, as it is the case for the first evaluation phase. The longitudinality of the second phase enables continuous measurement of both travellers' and platform's performance. The evaluation with service providers was remote, unmoderated and contextual (i.e. service providers completed the process and questionnaire at their own time and at their own place). Service providers completed the registration of their service on their own. Before

any process takes place, they were interviewed on their professional background, current and existing relevant experience and their expectations about the Service Registration Tool and process (i.e. pre-acceptance).

2.2. Evaluation with service providers

The first functional prototype was evaluated by 6 internal to the project service providers during the first iteration phase and another 15 externals to the project service providers in the second phase. The Service Registration Tool provides a simple and straightforward procedure and it will be offered through the MyCorridor platform as a web service. The Service Registration Tool (Figure 1) is an online tool which aims to automate the process of registering a service on the MaaS platform.

Figure 1. The Service Registration Repository (left) and the Service Registration Tool form (right).

The main functionalities offered are the following a) Service provider registration and login, b) Registration of a new service, c) Edit of an existing service, and d) View existing services.

2.2.1 Instruments of measurements

Testing scenarios were prepared to only guide the service providers in completing the accompanying diaries and not for traditional usability testing purposes. The service providers themselves assessed the process and the perceived effort, success and easiness. Three scenarios were prepared and shared through a service provider diary template. This diary was an online spreadsheet, with one sheet describing the scenarios and one to provide their comments and suggestions (log/diary). These steps were compared with the steps defined by the development team (i.e. Service provider log-in including registered service provider and new/unregistered service provider; service registration; service provider business rules editing). The baseline interview lasted approximately an hour. Interviews will be held via phone or Skype (or other online meeting applications). The main sections of the interview are a) Background information, b) Previous Experience/Current Behaviour, c) Constraints/Cost/Value, d) Risk/Impact.

The online service provider scenarios completion and log were filled in after the completion of each scenario. The participant will rate each scenario with regards to its ease of use with a 5-rating Likert scale, rate the success of completion of each scenario, add the steps taken to complete each scenario as well as give an estimate of time taken to complete each scenario. The Service Registration Tool and integration process evaluation (post-questionnaire) includes the following categories: a) Service Registration Tool use and performance, b) use of supportive documentation and examples, learnability, sustainability and maintainability, changeability, effort, Usability (standardised questionnaire, SUS scale (Brooke, 2013)). The evaluation session was completed within two hours. Users completed a General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) compliant consent form regardless if they are members of the Consortium or not.

2.3. Evaluation with travellers

In the first iteration phase, 25 travellers (commuters, tourists, businessmen, low ICT literacy users, mobility restricted users, spontaneous users and students) participated at each pilot site. However, a user might fit to more than one of these categories (e.g. a user can be both a mobility-restricted businessman and a commuter):

Background information of the identified users were collected before any testing takes place, also with the consideration of their mobility patterns and choices. Users will vary in age, type of user cluster, ICT literacy and education, occupational background, nationality, income and vehicle use.

The users were loosely matched to the testing scenarios with the sole aim to collect meaningful and appropriate data, aiming for users to fully realize the potential of the offered services through this single digital platform with diverse mobility choices (i.e. from daily travelling routines (commuter) to special occasions (tourists)).

A mixture of usability (i.e. testing scenarios, think aloud protocol) and user experience (i.e. the user is given a loose storyboard with very clear objectives) have been selected for the first iteration phase. The researcher may also ask the participant to 'think aloud' as they work on a scenario to better understand the participant's mental model for the scenario and his decision-making in real time. When the participant has completed a scenario, the researcher sets up the starting point for the next scenario and continues the test. Each evaluation session followed a standard procedure where users will be informed in native language about the project (layman presentation), its

developments (mainly the ones included in the evaluation), the test procedure, the handling of recorded data, and before testing starts their consent will be obtained. After the end of the session, users will be debriefed. Each session will be a scenario-based evaluation face-to-face meeting with the end user.

The MaaS mobile application will be the one-stop-shop where all internal and several external mobility services will be integrated. The travellers will be able to create their own profile, select from pre-defined or create customised MaaS packages. They will be able to use a trip planner to create a journey (if they wish) and then create a package, get one Mobility Token for all their travelling arrangements, complete transactions, collect loyalty points and receive discounts. The traveller will be able to use the application registered or unregistered, however personalised service provision is only feasible for registered users. This traveller solution will be available as iOS and Android mobile application (Figure 2).

Figure 2. The MaaS mobile application (main menu; left) and the mobile token (ticket) (right).

Assessment of current mobility products used was investigated to establish a comparable baseline. Firstly, assessment of current experiences and background information was collected from service providers and travellers through baseline interviews or freely completed forms of selected participants to investigate their transport and mobility preferences and patterns along with pre-acceptance of the MaaS mobile application and consumer behaviour (self-assessment).

Secondly, users will complete a storyboard with no use of the app but only the first part of the storyboard and they will be left to their own devices to reach the objective of the scenario. Figure 3 presents an example of user testing storyboard. The first paragraph of the storyboard was used for the baseline scenario (e.g. the user is informed about the origin and destination of the journey and sometimes about the modes he/she can use). As this might be a time-consuming part of the user testing session, only one baseline scenario will be completed by users (*observer assessment*). One or more user testing scenarios are accompanied by a storyboard. The storyboard is the user scenario that will be provided to the participants. The user testing scenarios will be available to the facilitator for assessing the scenario completion and making notes in a separate template.

The storyboard includes the story, the objectives and the steps the participant needs to take to complete the scenario (an example is shown in Figure 3). The story is allowing the participant to step into the user's shoes with accompanying clearly stated objectives. The aim is not to confuse the user within the story but to have clear objectives of what they have to achieve within a context of use and purpose as well as to add a realistic flair in the scenario.

STORYBOARD for TOURISTS

Elena is 33 years old, employed, tech savvy and ready to leave for a summer leave. She wants to travel from Athens to Naxos (up to this point constitutes the instructions also for baseline scenario) in the most comfortable way MaaS platform can offer. Elena has been informed by a friend about MaaS one-stop-shop and uses the MaaS app he shared with her via SMS (how users get to one-stop-shop is important for online visibility) to visit the site. She has only one week before she has to return to work and does not want to lose any minute and she decides she is not interested in an existing MaaS product but wants to select the services herself. She wants to take a taxi to Rafina, get the ferry to Naxos island and wants to use public transport during her stay in the island, so she can easily move around.

Objective: Imagine you are in Elena's position and want to purchase a customised MaaS product to comfortably travel as a tourist from Athens to Naxos with only one voucher to get a taxi [Service name] from home to Rafina port, then get a ferry [Service name] to Naxos island and there to use the bus [Service name] for a whole week in Naxos.

Figure 3. The MaaS mobile application (main menu; left) and the mobile token (ticket) (right).

The structure of the testing scenarios is presented in the following table (Table 1) with the main categories shown in the first column and a description of each category in the second column. These scenarios will be administered only to user testing facilitators for observation and their evaluation of the scenario completion.

Table 1. Testing scenario template

Goal/Output	<i>[The testing scenario title, main itinerary]</i>
UC - sub-UC	<i>[Use Case and sub-Use Cases titles, as defined within D1.1]</i>
Inputs	<i>[What is necessary to be in place in order to the user to be able to execute the scenario, e.g. the user might have to register first]</i>
Assumptions	<i>[The basic assumptions are fulfilled, e.g. the user is a commuter or an older traveller, as defined in the testing scenario goal]</i>
Steps	<i>[These are all separate steps required to complete each scenario. The user needs to complete all steps in order to complete the scenario unless stated otherwise]</i>
Success criteria	<i>[Defines the actions that need to be made or what is needed to be done by the user in order to the facilitator to decide that the scenario was successfully completed]</i>
Notes	<i>[These are notes to be taken into consideration by the facilitator that are important for the execution of the scenario]</i>

Each facilitator will be provided with a facilitator spreadsheet, where they will complete the following information for each scenario completed with task and scenario information (i.e. duration, success, attempts, pathways, think aloud remarks, etc.).

2.3.1. Instruments, metrics and questionnaires

The early phases will be mostly formative with selected summative aspects. The latter will mainly aim to create a comparative basis across phases and collection of summative data. Selected participants (5 participants per pilot site) will first complete the baseline interview/ questionnaire that comprises the following categories: a) Background information; b) Mobility needs & wants; c) Online consumer experience; d) MaaS awareness; e) MaaS mobile app pre-acceptance.

A pre-testing questionnaire that includes the following parts will be completed only by those participants that were not being interviewed. These participants will additionally answer the mobility needs and wants questions from the baseline interview: a) Background information; b) Computer literacy; c) Online consumer attitude and behaviour; d) Online shopping needs & wishes; e) MaaS awareness, f) MaaS platform pre-acceptance.

The following metrics will be collected per subject of evaluation.

Baseline experience: Formative data and content analysis of topics and themes under the four areas: A. Background information, B. Access Needs & Wants and MaaS awareness, C. Consumer experience, and D. MaaS pre-acceptance. The questionnaire consists of 24 question items (13 close-ended and 11 open-ended). Therefore, descriptive statistics will be prepared for the close-ended items and content analysis will be conducted for the remaining 11 open-ended items. A template to collect data from each pilot site will be circulated to partners. A content analysis will be conducted on aggregated and consolidated data across pilot sites. Comparison will be conducted for the following variables: a) user group membership, b) digital literacy, and c) socio Economic Status (SES). This evaluation is formative and purely qualitative. Pre-acceptance will be compared with acceptance at each evaluation phase (1st and 2nd).

Face-to-Face evaluation sessions:

Scenario completion (including baseline scenario completion): Success, duration, deviation from designed paths, screen capture of scenario completion, video and audio recordings (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Set up of usability sessions

Subjective measures included closed and open-ended question items: Pre- and post-questionnaire completion, SUS and TAP-3 (Brooke, 2013; Venkatsh & Balam 2008). standardised questionnaires.

Facilitator notes: emotion heuristics, observation notes from ‘think aloud’ protocol.

- **Completion Rates:** A simple gateway metric that constitutes a simple usability measure. We will measure if the user succeeds or fails to complete the scenario and subsequent steps (i.e. tasks).
- **Usability Problems:** these will be formative descriptions of the UI issues encountered by the user and the number (and type) of users encountering these issues. The severity of the problem (high/moderate/low) will be noted by the facilitator accompanied by a suggestion for solution (if any and if feasible). The knowledge of the potentially encountered problems can be used to calculate Return on Investment (ROI) and by knowing the type of users that have these problems can help the pilot teams to define what kind of problems are found by what kind of users and discovery rates per user group. That could better predict the sample size number we might need for the impact assessment.
- **Scenario Time:** Recording how long it takes the user to complete (or not) the scenario (seconds or minutes) will allow us to measure the productivity and efficiency for the specific scenario. Comparison of the completion times to the expert (researchers) can give an indication of the deviation, reasons and reveal any issues in the operation of the back-end and front-end mechanisms.
- **Scenario Level Satisfaction:** Users are asked to simply state how difficult it was to complete the scenario.
- **Errors:** Facilitators will record any mistakes, omissions while trying to complete the scenarios along with a very short description and a severity for the specific error. They will be checked along all identified UI issues to reveal any relations/ patterns.
- **Clicks:** Number of clicks required to complete the scenario. They are good indicators of efficiency and very often the first click is an indication of success or failure in completing the scenario at hand. For websites and web-applications, these fundamental tracking metrics might be objective indicators of usability.

2.3.6. Limitations

User testing within a MaaS study has several limitations because the mobile app is being developed during the project progresses and certain corridors and services are addressed per pilot site. Therefore, fully open and real-life testing is not possible because not all services that exist in this country and/ or region will be available at each site. As such, though, the second evaluation phase methodology incorporates realistic scenarios and collects data during real-life travelling experience, the users will be recruited and informed about the study purpose and its inherent limitations (i.e. semi-real-life experience). Such a perspective, allows for real data collection and at the same time avoids the dissatisfaction and disappointment that may result because of services and routes not addressed in the project, leading into artefacts being embedded in the evaluation.

3. Second evaluation phase: The semi-real experience

The second evaluation phase testing will entail evaluation with service providers and travellers. This is the final evaluation phase with the final version of the one-stop-shop with of all integrated services and involving real travellers. A less obvious objective is the meta-evaluation of the whole real-life experience and its interpretation for MaaS innovative transportation market in general for Europe and globally, much broader than MaaS project itself. The meta-evaluation process will take up the major inferences and lessons learnt and will translate them into recommendations for MaaS systems. Additionally, travellers’ user acceptance will be measured to estimate the penetration of MaaS to transportation, taking into consideration the continuously changing and disruptive ‘scenery’ (e.g. automation in private and public transportation, cooperative and IoT emergence).

3.1 Evaluation with service providers

The second evaluation phase with service providers will include the integration of the remaining services and the integration of external/ invited service providers. MaaS Consortium will sign a Memorandum of Understanding (MoU) with each one of the external service providers who want to integrate their service(s) to the MaaS platform. Therefore, the process might not differ significantly from the one described for the first evaluation phase. For example, an optimised version of the Service Registration Tool with additional supportive documentation, files and URLs will be evaluated. The evaluation material will be further refined to reflect the improvements and changes made, based on the first iteration results. Nevertheless, the baseline assessment will remain the same, as we have to collect background information for all service providers. As the process is not anticipated to differ significantly, increased effort is required to engage and attract service providers that will provide added value to the ecosystem-to-be, as well as aggregators offering bundles of services across countries. Therefore, a separate engagement strategy to attract external service providers to MaaS will be defined in close collaboration with the dissemination team along with the coordination and platform administrators.

3.2 Evaluation with travellers

Contrary to the second phase with service providers, the second evaluation phase with travellers is completely different when compared to the first one. The second evaluation phase will be conducted in semi-real conditions. As the existing MaaS mobile application will offer pre-defined services at certain areas, then the travellers will be recruited to complete real journeys and carry out real transactions (with no additional monetary gain/procurement for the aggregator/payment or any of the partners but solely for service providers that are (or not) members of this Consortium). Users will be compensated for their participation and reimbursed in case issues with their journeys and Mobility Tokens arise.

Again, recruitment, incentivisation and engagement are of instrumental role in the success of the second evaluation phase. Dedicated steps in the organization and logistics part of the project will be taken to ensure the appropriate travellers participate and at the same time achieve a wide enough diversity according to user profiles (e.g. commuter, student, etc.). The participants from the first iteration phase will participate in the second along another 30 travellers per pilot site (300 users in total). Recruiting the same participants across phases increases the comparability and, thus, the validity of the results. In addition, 10% of total users will participate in dedicated usability sessions to evaluate the usability and user experience of MaaS mobile application (the same evaluation material will be used in these dedicated sessions across all pilot sites, adjusted for improvements and changes in the second evaluation phase). Two dedicated workshops will take place at least a month prior kicking off the activities to: a) disseminate and discuss with partners the evaluation process, material, etc. and b) put in motion the recruitment and incentivisation processes, which are required to elicit continuous and frequent use of the platform to reflect selected types of journeys and package selection.

Users from relevant user groups will be identified and will be invited to participate in the second phase. As mentioned above, the travellers who will participate in the first phase will be included to the second in order to ensure continuous assessment from baseline to end of real tests across the lifecycle of the project and its developments. As scenarios will be pre-defined, then travellers will be recruited to complete specific routes and journeys, thus, the term semi-real is used to describe the second evaluation phase. Moreover, as the MaaS application will still be a prototype, participants will be reimbursed if they encounter problems, delays, etc. because of the MaaS app use. As such, potential users will be attracted through dedicated events for travellers and the existing networks of each pilot site. Users will be informed about the scenarios they will be asked to complete. The scenarios will be adjusted, and the users will be asked to carry at least 55% of their travelling within the week through MaaS. Users will be compensated for their participation and will receive real incentives and loyalty points. In addition, they will be reimbursed for their expenses in case they encounter issues during travelling because of MaaS use.

A dedicated testing version of the platform will be created to track the anonymised use of the recruited participants who will use the MaaS platform/mobile application anonymously (dedicated code per user) for a period of six months. Users will be informed about the packages and services available at their place of origin (depending the type of user) and suggested scenarios of use by the Pilot Site Managers (PSMs). Any respective limitations will be considered for re-adjustment of existing scenarios for real implementation.

Users will receive an information sheet with all data types collected during their participation and they will have to agree by signing the informed consent form. The consent form will include links to the data privacy and terms and conditions on using the MaaS application.

Apart from the web analytics continuously collected during the use of the MaaS platform, users will keep a diary with specific aspects of their journey (e.g. purpose of journey, likes/dislikes of the specific journey, delays, problems encountered, mood, evaluate each journey experience as a whole, and in general, add thoughts about each specific journey they make). In addition, an online feedback tool (i.e. through reminders and notifications) will be put in place to collect their experience, acceptance, satisfaction, worse and best moments of use including any recommendations of problems/issues encountered.

A contact team (for real-life tests) will be allocated to serve as a contact point for users in case of any issues arise. Users will participate in a workshop prior kicking off the real-life testing activities where all aspects of testing and participation will be thoroughly explained, and they will have the opportunity to raise questions and discuss any issues with the evaluation team. These workshops will take place at each pilot site and they will signify the beginning of the second evaluation phase with travellers. Travellers who did not participate in the first phase will complete the baseline assessment and the pre-questionnaire.

Each completed diary can be either in paper form or online and it will be submitted weekly in order the respective evaluation team to keep track of participant's motivation, learning curve, change in travelling behaviour and modal choices.

The objective is to evaluate the true experience of the traveller, their preferences and the MaaS and, consequently, MaaS penetration into their daily travelling patterns. The findings will have high ecological validity and many of the data will be further fed to the impact assessment calculations.

Additional focus groups with travellers as well as stakeholders (e.g. representatives from authorities, regional transport agencies, touristic agencies, mobility and MaaS aggregators, public transport -and other type of vehicles- operators, infomobility and added value providers, mobile and technology service providers, etc.) will be held at the end of the second evaluation phase; firstly, to collect qualitative data to triangulate data collection and enrich the other types of collected data and, secondly, to conduct the supplementary impact assessment based on MAMCA. Focus groups with stakeholders will aim to collect information about the sustainability and growth of MaaS as a business and consumer experience after the end of the project with consideration on new directions/innovations in transportation, such as IoT and automation apart from MaaS. At least two focus groups (i.e. one with travellers and one with stakeholders) will take place at each pilot site. The focus groups with stakeholders will be sought to be organized within a major project event near the end of the project.

It is important to calculate customer related experience data (Customer Experience; CX) because the MaaS platform aims to offer paid mobility products/ services, hence return of investment/mission and conversion rates are relevant and important. Collected metrics will include: Consumption/use of mobility product, Frequency of use, Preferred mobility products/ services, Preferred combination of products/ services, Ratio of use of added value synthetic services, Preferred MaaS packages, Preferred payment method (if applicable), Frequency of visit, Preferences popularity (which user preferences are popular per traveller type), Time spent on platform per visit,

Completed transactions, Cancelled transactions, Preferred redeemed coupons, Most popular incentive, Ratio of registered/vs. unregistered users, Preferred entry point(s), Preferences per type of user for all the above, % of private car use (ratio for reduced use), Use/consumption of ‘greener’ packages, Use/consumption of ‘greener’ mobility products/ services (e.g. PT, bike sharing, etc.), Change in modal choice and travelling behaviour (patterns), Ratios modal split (positive increase ratio), Attitude/change in attitude towards ‘greener’ mobility.

As analytics of User Experience, the MyCorridor platform analytics will be utilised to continuously collect data of MaaS platform use whilst travelers will be on the go. Apart from diaries and online feedback forms that will allow us to collect their subjective feedback and perceive journey experience, we will collaborate with transport operators to collect information about successful journey completions (or not) and successful Mobility Token redemptions (or not) to further validate their experience with objective data.

4. User testing preliminary results

Users were able to create an account, set their own travelling preferences and profile and either create a MaaS package by selecting the services they want (My Packs) or create a MaaS package based on the trip they were planning to take (MaaS on the Go).

When writing this paper, the first evaluation phase has been completed and the second is being organized. Hence, only very early results exist, and a high level overview is presented here. Over 119 individuals participated in the pilots across all 5 pilot sites with almost half of them being knowledgeable about MaaS, but only 25% having being informed by the press or other articles and over 83% of them buying mobility products, e.g. bus (31%), train tickets (66%) and plane (54%) tickets online. Important factors in relation to the acceptance of the offered MaaS solution where the indicators presented in Figure 5. All dimensions are higher than 60% and are good indicators of future adherence.

Figure 5. Trust, easiness and value of MyC application (% of users)

5. Conclusion

The specifications and primary dimensions of this methodological for the development of MaaS solutions from the early design to the actual deployment in real-life conditions as well as the evaluation for the professionals and organizations offering their services through this mobile application via one unified ticket (i.e. Mobility Token). Addressing different facets of an ecosystem-to-be requires borrowing and combining evaluation techniques from various areas of research.

Overall, acceptance is above average even for the first version of this MaaS app. The next steps entail the in-depth analyses of the results that will be used to improve the mobile application, estimate the impact of the MyCorridor application can have on the MaaS and, generally, transportation world and identify the effective social and monetary incentives for future use and adoption. The results will be used to improve the current MaaS solutions’ prototypes and improve the travellers’ and providers’ experiences.

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